

SmartOffline NextGen: SW Architecture and Applications

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Abstract—Today robots represents a key factor in several industry fields as far as productivity and competitiveness are concerned. To this purpose, offline programming approaches and tools are clearly needed in order to allow fine development and fast adaptation of robot programs while minimizing machine downtime. In this context, this work introduces the offline programming software developed by SACMI in collaboration with IT-I, named “SmartOffline NextGen”.

Index Terms—robot programming, offline programming

I. INTRODUCTION & PROBLEM SETTING

Nowadays, robots are becoming key elements in increasing manufacturing competitiveness. Nevertheless, widespread adoption of robotic technologies in small-to-medium sized enterprises is still undermined by certain well-known factors, among which the inherently complex and time-consuming nature of robot programming surely plays a crucial role [1]. Traditional methods for robot programming typically consist in either using the robot teach pendant or in simulating the robot task inside an offline programming (OLP) environment [2], [3]. In the first case, not only the operator needs to learn how to properly use the teach pendant, but the inherent point-to-point programming style is inefficient whenever the realization of complex programs is approached.

As a matter of fact, in this scenario the whole programming time turns out to be machine downtime, with possible significant impacts on the robot’s productivity. On the other hand, the OLP approach allows the programmer to develop at least a first draft of the complete program without having to stop the robot, thus limiting machine downtime to the time needed to realize the final validation of the program [4]. State-of-the-art approaches to the OLP problems are typically based on CAD-CAM approaches where programs are semi-automatically derived from CAD drawings [5], [6]. More recent approaches demonstrate the integration of OLP environments with technologies such as mixed reality, like for instance [7].

Independently from the specific approaches, OLP is almost unanimously considered the most efficient solution to the problem of robot programming, as argued in [8]. Given these considerations, the fact that SACMI opted for the OLP approach for the programming of their robotized cells comes at no surprise. To this regard, this work presents our approach

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to the problem of OLP and introduces our software, named “SmartOffline NextGen” (SmOffNG). The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II explains the general concepts that led the developments of SmOffNG, while Section III presents an overview of the SW architecture of the proposed solution. Finally, Section IV provides examples of applications in the ceramic industry.

II. GENERAL CONCEPTS

In this Section, a review of the principal concepts that led the development of SmOffNG is presented. Let us start from the goals of our solution, which can be listed as follows:

- **Programming**: offer a comprehensive OLP platform for the robotics applications currently developed by SACMI in the context of the ceramic-sanitaryware sector;
- **Virtualization**: allow digital twinning of the aforementioned robotics applications also for simulation purposes;
- **Usability**: facilitate the development of complex programs by users that do not have a strong background in robotics and robotic technologies.

Given this goals, the design and the development of SmOffNG have revolved around the following key concepts:

- **Cell**: the root of the tree structure that models the virtualized cell. See Figure 1;
- **Robot**: a machine endowed with one or more DoFs. It can be either an anthropomorphic manipulator or an auxiliary machine (i.e. a linear axis or a turning table);
- **Work-Item**: a generic physical object that can model either the work-piece that is processed during the program or an auxiliary object, like for instance a prohibited area. It is modelled by means of a triangular mesh;
- **Via-Point (VP)**: a destination that a robot needs to reach, specified in the form of either joint or operational space coordinates. A detail breakdown of the additional attributes defining a VP is given in table II. In case the virtualized cell contains more than one robot, a VP will contain a destination for each virtualized robot;
- **Segment**: an interpolated trajectory (sampled at a fixed time step) connecting two consecutive VPs;
- **Trace**: an ordered list of VPs, connected by Segments;
- **Program**: an ordered list of Traces, see Figure 2;

As far as the definition of VPs and the interpolation of the Segments are concerned, SmOffNG was developed in order to identify the following problems:

- **Reachability**: either a VP or an interpolated point lies outside the reachable workspace of at least one robot;

Fig. 1. Example of Tree Structure modelling a robotized cell.

- **Singularity:** during a motion interpolated in the Cartesian Space an anthropomorphic manipulator assumes a singular configuration;
- **Collision:** either a VP or an interpolated point are characterized by an interference between two physical objects (links, tools, work-items).

Finally, beside the definition of VPs, Traces and Programs, the main features offered by SmOffNG can be listed as follows:

- **Interactive 3D View:** 3D visualization with the possibility to move VPs and physical objects;
- **Animation:** simulated execution of a Trace/Program by animating robots within the 3D view;
- **Collision Checking:** selection of specific pairs of physical objects and identification of possible collision between them during Trace interpolation;
- **Process Simulation:** physics-based simulation of the task, currently available only for glazing applications (see Subsection IV-A for further details);
- **Exporting:** conversion of a defined Program in a format that can be executed on a physical robot. SmOffNG can export programs for Gaiotto [9] proprietary robots and for several commercial vendors.

III. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The main idea behind the design of SmOffNG consists in decoupling the algorithmic portion from the desktop application, as it is shown in Figure 3. The first component is called “BuildServer” and it is responsible for computing the direct and inverse kinematics of the robots that are virtualized inside

Fig. 2. Program breakdown.

the cell, and for interpolating a continuous trajectories among the various VP defined by the user (sampled at a fixed time step of 0.04 s). On the other hand the desktop application, simply named “Client”, acts mainly as HMI, allowing the user to build and modify the virtualized cell, instantiate programs, traces and VPs, and simulate the execution of either programs or traces. The information exchange between the two components is realized via a gRPC [10] interface.

As a matter of fact, this decoupled approach entails several advantages. First, it enables the co-existence of different programming languages and development platforms, thus making it possible to select the most suitable combination of language/platform with respect to the requirements of each SW component. For instance, in our specific case the BuildServer is realized in Python, while the Client is written in C# on a .Net platform.

In addition, this solution allows to realize the deployment diagram pictured in Figure 4. Let us assume that the user develops a SmOffNG Program for a specific model of work-piece. According to the scheme, each time an instance of this work-piece enters the plant, the inspection system measures its displacement with respect to the nominal position defined inside SmOffNG. This information is then forwarded to the BuildServer instance running on the so-called “Panel-PC”. The BuildServer loads the Program (whose serialization has been previously loaded on the Panel-PC via shared memory access), configures the coordinates of the main work-item’s base according to the measured displacement, and finally recompiles the program taking into account this offset. In case recompilation is successful, the BuildServer will export the robot program that will be transferred to the robot controller for execution. Otherwise, it will output one or more error messages to inform the user about reachability, singularity or collision problems that emerged after the offset was applied.

Even though this solution requires programs to be recompiled each time a work-piece enters the plant, it prevents the robot to stop due to reachability, singularity and collision problems after the execution of the program has started. Given the fact that resuming production after this kind of stop is a delicate and time-consuming operation, we believe that our approach will optimize productivity.

TABLE I
BREAKDOWN OF THE ADDITIONAL ATTRIBUTES DEFINING A VIA-POINT

Attribute	Data-Type	Unit	Values/Range	Notes
Description	Text	NAV	NAV	Named possibly assigned to the VP by the programmer
Movement Type	Enum	NAV	Joint / Cartesian	Interpolation strategy for the connection between the current VP and the following one
Linear Speed	Real	m/s	≥ 0.00	Cruise speed value, used in case of Cartesian motion
Joint Speed	Integer	%	$[0, 100]$	Override of joint speed, used in case of joint motion
Approximation	Integer	%	$[0, 100]$	Reach exactly the defined VP (0) - approximate motion to preserve cruise speed (100)
Pause	Real	s	blank $\cup \geq 0.00$	If a value is set, the robot reaches exactly the VP and waits for the specified time
Active Tool	Enum	NAV	NAV	Tool to be used once VP is reached. Selected among available tools defined on robot
Active TCP	Enum	NAV	NAV	TCP to be set once VP is reached. Selected among available TCPs defined on active Tool
Digital Outputs	Array of Boolean	NAV	<i>True / False</i>	Array of Digital Outputs values to be actuated once VP is reached
Analog Outputs	Array of Real	TBD	TBD	Array of Analog Outputs values to be actuated once VP is reached

Fig. 3. SmOffNG SW architecture.

IV. APPLICATIONS

As far as the applications are concerned, at the moment SmOffNG is used to develop glazing and superficial finishing programs for applications in the ceramic industry. In the following, specific features related to each task are discussed.

A. Glazing

With respect to glazing applications, SmOffNG implements two dedicated features: the templization of the analog outputs and process simulation. The first feature allows the user to create combinations of values of the analog outputs (also referred as technological parameters) so that the combination of values can be assigned to several VPs. In the context of glazing, the following analog outputs have been considered:

- **Flow:** mass flow of the product to be sprayed, typically expressed in g/min ;
- **Cap:** atomization pressure, typically expressed in $mBar$;
- **Fan:** spraying cone opening pressure, also typically expressed in $mBar$.

Moving to process simulation, Figure 5 shows an example of a glazing program. The simulation is based on a physical model of the spraying process that estimates the amount of material transferred to the work-item on the basis of:

- a probabilistic distribution;
- the geometry of a spraying cone, which in turn is defined on the basis of the Cap and Fan parameters;
- some physical parameters of the sprayed fluid, like for instance its density and drying factor.

The process simulation is realized by computing physical model at each finely interpolated point belonging to each Segment of the active Trace, thus computing both the overall mass amount of material delivered to the work-item and the

thickness of the sprayed layer on each triangle composing the work-item mesh. Furthermore, by combining simulations computed along all the Traces, it is possible to obtain the simulation corresponding to the complete Program. The thickness scale pictured in Figure 6 can be configured in terms of both discretization and lower/upper values.

B. Finishing

Moving to the superficial finishing task, the distinctive feature implemented by SmOffNG consists in the management of the collisions between the abrasive tools (that are characterized by passive mechanical compensation acting along their approach direction) and the work-item. taking also into account that contact between the tool and the work-item is mandatory in order to perform the task, the output of the collision checking in the context of finishing is slightly more complex, as it is shown in Figure 7. More in detail:

- **No Collision:** no contact between tool and work-item;
- **Desired Contact:** tool is in contact with the work-item and all compensation is available;
- **Intermediate Collision:** tool is in contact with the work-item and compensation is partially available;
- **Critical Collision:** tool is in rigid contact with the work-item, i.e. no more compensation is available;

For the sake of completeness, the technological parameters that can be templated are the following:

- **Rotation Pressure:** pressure to activate rotation of the abrasive tool, typically expressed in $mBar$;
- **Compensation Pressure:** pressure to activate compensation of the abrasive tool, typically expressed in $mBar$;

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Fig. 4. SmOffING SW/HW deployment diagram.

Fig. 5. Example of glazing program. VPs are highlighted as black arrows.

Fig. 6. Example of spraying simulation output, with a 5-level thickness gradient on the left.

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Fig. 7. Types of collision checking outputs for compensated tools.